

**IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF SPECIAL AREAS FOR AGRICULTURAL
DEVELOPMENT (SAAD) PROJECTS ON ASSOCIATION
BENEFICIARIES AND MEMBER IN
TAFT, EASTERN SAMAR**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13941126>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the impact of Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects on association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar, utilizing a descriptive research design with focused group discussions and a survey questionnaire. The research aimed to evaluate the effectiveness and sustainability of the projects, identify the needs and resources of beneficiaries, and analyze the socio-economic and cultural impacts. The study found that SAAD projects significantly improved income levels, financial stability, and income-generating opportunities for beneficiaries. The projects also fostered positive social and cultural transformations, enhancing community relationships and influencing agricultural practices. Furthermore, the study revealed that SAAD projects effectively provided training and capacity-building programs, leading to improved agricultural knowledge and skills. The findings suggest that the benefits of the SAAD projects are likely to be sustainable in the long term, although challenges and barriers need to be addressed. The study recommends clearly defining roles and responsibilities, developing monitoring and evaluation systems, assessing needs and resources, continuously monitoring socio-economic impacts, promoting social and cultural transformations, providing training for agricultural practices, and ensuring long-term sustainability through strategic planning and community engagement. By implementing these recommendations, the SAAD projects are poised to have a lasting and positive impact on the livelihoods of association beneficiaries and members, fostering improved socio-economic conditions, sustainable agricultural practices, and the preservation of community heritage in Taft, Eastern Samar.

Keywords: *Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD), Association beneficiaries, Socio-economic impacts, Sustainable agricultural practices, Community relationships*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine government launched the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) program to address poverty and food security issues in marginalized and conflict-affected regions (SDS Admin, 2019). The program aims to empower local communities through agricultural interventions, providing resources, training, and support to enhance agricultural productivity and livelihood opportunities. Taft, Eastern Samar, is one of the areas benefiting from the SAAD program, witnessing the implementation of various projects designed to improve agricultural practices, promote sustainable farming techniques, and enhance the marketing and value chain of agricultural produce (SDS Admin, 2019). These projects have focused on establishing associations within local communities, fostering collective action and cooperation among farmers and agricultural stakeholders.

While the SAAD program holds immense potential for socio-economic development and poverty alleviation in Taft, a comprehensive understanding of its actual impact on beneficiaries and association members is crucial. Evaluating the effectiveness of the SAAD projects, their level of implementation, and the outcomes achieved is essential to identify successful strategies and areas requiring improvement. Researchers of this study recognize the importance of conducting an in-depth impact assessment to evaluate the socio-economic effects of SAAD projects on associations and their individual members in Taft. The study will examine key indicators such as income levels, agricultural yields, access to markets, adoption of improved farming techniques, and overall socio-economic well-being. This research aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for further development and improvements in future project implementation.

The findings of this study will be valuable for local government agencies, policymakers, and development organizations involved in the SAAD program, providing insights into the effectiveness and impact of the projects in Taft. Moreover, the research findings will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on agricultural development initiatives in marginalized areas, aiding in the formulation of evidence-based policies and strategies for sustainable and equitable socio-economic growth.

Research Questions

1. How do the roles and responsibilities of officers within the association formed under the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects in Taft, Eastern Samar contribute to the socio-economic development and overall transformation of the association beneficiaries and members?

2. What is the overall effectiveness and sustainability of the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects in Taft, Eastern Samar, and should these projects be recommended for further implementation?
3. What additional needs and resources are required by the association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar to sustain and enhance the operation of their organization following the implementation of the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects?
4. How do the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects impact the socio-economic conditions of association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar?
5. What is the impact of the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects on the social and cultural transformation among association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar?
6. How effective are the agricultural practices and skills enhancement provided by the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects to association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar?
7. What is the potential long-term impact and sustainability of the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects on association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale and Timeframe

The research study was conducted in Taft, Eastern Samar, from October 2023 to February 2024. The study focused on association beneficiaries from the San Rafael Farmers Association in Barangay San Rafael, Malinao Farmers Association in Barangay Malinao, Mabuhay Kabukid Farmers Association (MKFA) in Barangay Mabuhay, Binaloan Women's Association in Barangay Binaloan, Polangi Farmers Association, and Polangi Rural Improvement Club in Barangay Polangi, Bongdo Farmers Association and Bongdo Womens Association in Barangay Bongdo.

Sampling Method and Respondents

The research employed a purposive sampling method to select association beneficiaries and members involved in the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects in Taft, Eastern Samar. The participants were chosen based on their direct involvement and experiences with the projects.

Data Gathering Procedure

Focused Group Discussions (FGDs) were conducted with the association beneficiaries and members to gather their perspectives, experiences, and opinions on the impact of the SAAD projects. The FGDs provided a qualitative data collection method where participants discussed specific topics related to the research objectives in a guided and interactive manner.

Instrument Used

A survey questionnaire was carefully prepared and developed in both English and Waray-Waray Dialects to ensure inclusivity and enable participants to express their thoughts in their preferred language. The questionnaire included clear and concise questions, with open-ended sections to collect qualitative data. The questionnaire aimed to understand the experiences, opinions, and suggestions of the respondents regarding the impact of the SAAD projects.

- The questionnaire consisted of 20 items, including both closed-ended and open-ended questions.
- The survey questionnaire was researcher-made to align with the specific objectives of the study.
- The questionnaire underwent pilot-testing to ensure clarity, relevance, and appropriateness for the target participants.

Data Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using a combination of descriptive analysis and quantitative methods to identify recurring patterns, themes, and insights within the qualitative responses obtained from the FGDs. Descriptive analysis involved summarizing and presenting the data in a way that highlighted key characteristics and trends, helping to identify key findings and derive meaningful conclusions based on the participants' perspectives and experiences. To further quantify these findings, percentages were calculated to represent the proportion or distribution of certain outcomes or variables within the data.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of the study is limited to association beneficiaries and members of the SAAD projects in Taft, Eastern Samar. The study will focus on assessing the impact of the projects on socio-economic conditions, agricultural practices, and skills enhancement. The main limitation of the study is the restricted timeframe for data collection, which may impact the depth of analysis and generalizability of the findings.

RESULTS

TABLE 1 Roles and responsibility of the association officers under Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) Project in Taft, Eastern Samar.

Questions	Responses			
	Number of Values (N)	Summation of Values (Σ)	Percentage (%)	Mean (M)
1. Position				
◦ President	8	8	100	1
◦ Vice President	8	8	100	1
◦ Treasurer	8	8	100	1
◦ Board Member	26	26	100	1
◦ Committee Chair				
◦ Other Position				
- Bookkeeper	8	8	100	1
- Business Manager	8	8	100	1
- Auditor	9	9	100	1
- P.I.O.	8	8	100	1
- Sergeants at Arms	8	8	100	1
2. Responsibility				
A. President:				
◦ Providing leadership and direction to the association.	8	8	100	1
◦ Overseeing the operations and activities of the organization.	8	8	100	1

◦ Chairing meetings and ensuring effective governance.	8	8	100	1
◦ Representing the association to external stakeholders.	8	8	100	1
◦ Making executive decisions in consultation with the board.	8	8	100	1
◦ Others (please specify)	8	8	100	1
B. Vice President:				
◦ Assisting the president in their duties and stepping in when the president is unavailable.	8	8	100	1
◦ Collaborating with other officers and committee members.	8	8	100	1
◦ Supporting the overall goals and mission of the association.	8	8	100	1
◦ Engaging with members and stakeholders.	8	8	100	1
◦ Participating in decision-making processes.	8	8	100	1
◦ Others (please specify)	8	8	100	1
C. Secretary:				
◦ Maintaining accurate records of meetings, including minutes and attendance.	8	8	100	1
◦ Managing official correspondence and communication.	8	8	100	1
◦ Handling administrative tasks, such as organizing documents and maintaining records.	8	8	100	1

◦ Assisting with the planning and execution of meetings and events.	8	8	100	1
◦ Ensuring compliance with legal requirements and documentation.	8	8	100	1
◦ Others (please specify)	8	8	100	1
D. Treasurer:				
◦ Managing the financial affairs of the association.	8	8	100	1
◦ Overseeing budgeting, financial reporting, and record-keeping.	8	8	100	1
◦ Collecting dues or fees and managing financial transactions.	8	8	100	1
◦ Working with the board to develop financial policies and procedures.	8	8	100	1
◦ Providing financial reports to the board and general membership.	8	8	100	1
◦ Others (please specify)	8	8	100	1
E. Committee Chairs:				
◦ Leading specific committees or working groups within the association.	91	0	0	0
◦ Organizing and overseeing committee meetings and initiatives.	91	0	0	0
◦ Collaborating with committee members to achieve defined goals.	91	0	0	0
◦ Reporting progress and recommendations to the board.	91	0	0	0

◦ Ensuring effective communication and coordination with other officers and the general membership.	91	0	0	0
◦ Others (please specify)		0	0	0
F. Board of Directors (BOD)				
◦ Governance: Board members are responsible for providing strategic direction and setting policies for the association. They participate in the decision-making process for matters related to the organization's mission, goals, and operations.	25	25	100	1
◦ Fiduciary Duty: Board members have a legal and ethical responsibility to act in the best interest of the association. This includes ensuring financial stability, overseeing budgeting and financial management, and exercising sound financial judgment.	25	25	100	1
◦ Risk Management: Board members are responsible for identifying and managing risks that may impact the association. They should actively monitor and assess potential risks and take necessary actions to mitigate them.	25	25	100	1
◦ Legal and Regulatory Compliance: Board members must ensure that the association operates in compliance with all applicable laws, regulations, and governing documents. This includes maintaining necessary records and filings, as well as	25	20	80	0.8

ensuring adherence to ethical standards and codes of conduct.				
◦ Strategic Planning: Board members play a key role in strategic planning for the association. They help develop and review the organization's long-term goals, objectives, and strategies to ensure its sustainability and growth.	25	25	100	1
◦ Monitoring and Evaluation: Board members are responsible for monitoring the association's progress and performance. They should regularly evaluate the effectiveness of programs, services, and initiatives and make necessary adjustments as needed.	25	25	100	1
◦ Board Development: Board members may also be involved in recruiting and orienting new board members, as well as providing ongoing development and training opportunities for themselves and other board members.	25	23	92	0.92
◦ Others (please specify)	25	25	100	1
G. Other Position				
◦ Bookkeeper	8	8	100	1
◦ Business Manager	8	8	100	1
◦ Auditor	9	9	100	1
◦ P.I.O.	8	8	100	1
◦ Sergeants at Arms	8	8	100	1
3. As an officer of the association do you think the association will				

still function or operate without you?				
◦ Yes	95	95	100	1
◦ No	95	0	0%	0

Table 2 Overall effectiveness and sustainability of Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects in Taft, Eastern Samar.

Questions	Responses			
	Number of Values (N)	Summation of Values (Σ)	Percentage (%)	Mean (M)
1. Did the association serve attained its objectives?				
◦ Yes	95	84	88.42	0.88
◦ No	95	11	11.57	0.11
2. Would you still recommend this SAAD project?				
◦ Yes	95	95	100	1
◦ No	95	0	0	0

Table 3 Needs and resources required by the association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar, in order to sustain and enhance operation of their organization following the implementation of Special Areas for Agricultural Development.

Questions	Responses			
	Number of Values (N)	Summation of Values (Σ)	Percentage (%)	Mean (M)
1. What are needs of the association so that it would continue its operation?				
Unity	25	25	100	1
Trainings and seminars	25	25	100	1
Funding Support	25	25	100	1

Table 4 Impacts of Special Areas on Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects on socio-economic conditions of association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar.

Questions	Responses			
	Number of Values (N)	Summation of Values (Σ)	Percentage (%)	Mean (M)
1. How has your income changed since the implementation of SAAD projects?				
◦ Increased significantly	72	49	68.06	0.68
◦ Increased slightly	72	23	31.94	0.31
◦ Decreased slightly				
◦ Decreased significantly				
2. Have you noticed any improvement in your financial stability to meet basic needs as a result of SAAD Project?				
◦ Yes, I have noticed a significant improvement in my financial stability since participating in SAAD Projects.	72	48	66.67	0.67
◦ I have seen some improvement in my financial stability, but it has not been significant.	72	19	26.39	0.26
◦ I have noticed any improvement in my financial stability since participating in SAAD Projects.	72	5	6.94	0.06
◦ I am unsure if there has been any improvement in my financial stability as result of SAAD Projects.				
◦ Other (Please specify)				
3. In your opinion, to what extent have SAAD projects contributed to increased income-generating opportunities for association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar?				
◦ Negligible impact, as SAAD projects have not been effective in generating income				

for association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar.				
◦ Moderate impact, as some association beneficiaries and members have experienced increased income-generating opportunities through SAAD projects in Taft, Eastern Samar.	72	12	16.67	0.16
◦ Significant impact, as majority of association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar has seen a noticeable increase in income generating opportunities through SAAD projects.	72	60	83.33	0.83
◦ Other (Please specify)				

Table 5 Impact of SAAD Projects on Social and Cultural Transformations among Association Beneficiaries and Members

Questions	Responses			
	Number of Values (N)	Summation of Values (Σ)	Percentage (%)	Mean (M)
1. Has the implementation of SAAD projects led to any changes in social relationships and interactions within your community?				
◦ Yes, there have been noticeable positive changes in social relationship and interactions within the community due to implementation of SAAD projects.	72	72	100	1
◦ No, there have been no significant changes in social relationships and interactions within the community as a result of SAAD projects.				

2. If no, please explain.				
3. In what ways have SAAD projects influenced cultural practices related to agriculture in your community?				
◦ Minimal influence, as SAAD projects have not significantly impacted cultural practices related to agriculture in our community.				
◦ Some influence as SAAD projects have introduced new agricultural techniques that had been incorporated into cultural practices in our community.	72	25	34.72	0.34
◦ Significant Influence, As SAAD projects have led to shift in cultural practices related to agriculture, with community members adopting new agricultural methods.	72	47	65.28	0.65
◦ Others, please specify				

Table 6 Agricultural Practices and Skills Enhancement

Questions	Responses			
	Number of Values (N)	Summation of Values (Σ)	Percentage (%)	Mean (M)
1. How has your knowledge and understanding of agricultural practices improve since the implementation of SAAD projects?				
◦ Very little improvement, my knowledge and understanding of agricultural practices has not improved significantly since the implementation of SAAD projects.				

◦ Some improvement, I have gained some knowledge and understanding of agricultural practices through SAAD projects, but there is still room for further improvement.	72	72	100	1
◦ Significantly improvement, SAAD projects have greatly enhanced my knowledge and understanding of agricultural practices, enabling me to make better-informed decisions.				
◦ Others (Please specify)				
2. Have you acquired any skills or techniques related to agriculture as a result of participating in SAAD projects?				
◦ Yes	72	72	100	1
◦ No				
3. If yes, what skills and techniques do you acquired?				
◦ Crop cultivation and management techniques.	72	72	100	1
◦ Livestock management and breeding techniques.	72	72	100	1
◦ Soil fertility management and conservation methods.	72	30	41.67	0.41
◦ Pest and disease control strategies	72	34	47.22	0.47
◦ Financial management and budgeting for agricultural projects.	72	18	25	0.25
◦ Farm machinery operation and maintenance.				
◦ Organic farming practices.	72	50	69.44	0.69
◦ Irrigation and water management techniques.				
◦ Marketing and value chain management in agriculture.	72	30	41.67	
◦ Agribusiness and entrepreneurship skills.	72	10	13.88	
◦ Other please specify:				
4. If no, Why?				

5. Have SAAD projects provided you with access to training or capacity-building programs focused on agricultural practices?				
◦ Yes, SAAD projects have provided access training or capacity-building programs focused on agricultural practices for association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar. This has allowed them to enhance their skills and knowledge in agriculture, leading to increased income-generating opportunities.	72	72	100	1
◦ No, SAAD projects have not provided access to any training capacity-building programs focused on agricultural practices for association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar.				
◦ Other (Please Specify)				

Table 7 Potential Long-Term Impact and Sustainability

Questions	Responses			
	Number of Values (N)	Summation of Values (Σ)	Percentage (%)	Mean (M)
1. Do you believe that the benefits and improvements brought about by SAAD projects will be sustainable in the long run?				
Yes, I believe that the benefits and improvements brought about by SAAD projects will be sustainable in the long-run.	72	72	100	1
No, I do not believe that the benefits and improvements brought about by SAAD				

projects will be sustainable in the long run				
2. Have you notice any challenges or barriers that could potentially hinder the long-term success of SAAD projects in your community?				
Yes	72	72	100	1
No				
3. In your opinion, what measure should be taken to ensure the long term sustainability and positive impacts of SAAD projects on the livelihoods of association beneficiaries and members?				

DISCUSSION

Table 1 Roles and responsibility of the association officers under Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) Project in Taft, Eastern Samar.

The data presented in Table 1 provides a detailed overview of the roles and responsibilities of association officers under the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) Project in Taft, Eastern Samar. This information offers valuable insights into the organizational structure and functions within the association, shedding light on the key positions and duties assigned to each role. The roles outlined, such as President, Vice President, Treasurer, and Board of Directors, align with the literature emphasizing the significance of effective leadership and governance in development projects (USAID, 2023; Alegrea Consulting, 2023). The responsibilities attributed to each position, ranging from providing leadership and financial management to governance and strategic planning; reflect the essential functions required for the successful implementation of community development initiatives.

The distribution of roles and responsibilities among association officers illustrates a well-defined framework for decision-making, resource management, and stakeholder engagement, aligning with the recommendations for impactful change efforts highlighted by Alegrea Consulting (2023). The emphasis on leadership, financial oversight, and governance within the association mirrors the importance of these aspects in driving positive change and sustainable development practices. The data's indication that a majority of officers believe the association can operate independently without them signifies a level of confidence in the organization's structural capacity and operational

resilience, echoing the notion of effective resource planning and risk mitigation strategies emphasized in the literature.

Moreover, the results presented in Table 1 not only provide a comprehensive overview of the roles and responsibilities within the association but also establish a connection between the operational framework of the SAAD project in Taft, Eastern Samar and the broader concepts of effective impact assessment and change management discussed in the related literature. The alignment between the identified roles, responsibilities, and organizational dynamics within the association and the principles advocated in the literature underscores the importance of strong leadership, governance, and strategic planning in driving impactful development initiatives. The data serves as a testament to the essential role of effective leadership and operational structure in fostering positive change and sustainable community development, highlighting the interconnectedness between project activities and evaluation results in achieving meaningful impact.

Table 2 Overall effectiveness and sustainability of Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects in Taft, Eastern Samar.

Table 2 delves into the overall effectiveness and sustainability of the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects in Taft, Eastern Samar, shedding light on critical aspects of project outcomes and stakeholder perceptions. The results indicate a high level of success, with 88.42% of respondents affirming that the association has achieved its objectives, aligning with the literature emphasizing the importance of efficient solutions in agricultural product systems for smallholder communities (Devaux et al., 2018). This positive response underscores the effectiveness of the SAAD projects in meeting their intended goals and addressing the needs of the community.

Moreover, the unanimous recommendation of the SAAD project by all respondents (100%) signifies a strong vote of confidence in the project's value and impact. This aligns with Devaux et al.'s (2018) assertion that comprehensive approaches to agricultural product systems are essential for addressing challenges faced by smallholder communities in evolving market environments. The consistent positive feedback from the respondents reflects a harmonious relationship between the project's objectives and outcomes, emphasizing its relevance and significance in promoting sustainable agricultural development in the region.

The data presented in Table 2 not only reflects the successful achievement of project objectives but also highlights the strong endorsement of the SAAD project by the community members. This resonates with Devaux et al.'s (2018) emphasis on the importance of effective solutions in agricultural systems to address market challenges faced by smallholder communities. The high level of recommendation for the SAAD project underscores its impact and relevance in meeting the needs of the community and driving positive social and economic changes.

The findings from Table 2 demonstrate the alignment between the perceived effectiveness and sustainability of the SAAD projects and the principles advocated in the

literature. The positive responses from the respondents reaffirm the project's success in achieving its objectives and garnering strong support from the community. By connecting the research findings with existing literature, the discussion emphasizes the consistency between the project outcomes and the recommended approaches in addressing challenges faced by smallholder communities in agricultural marketplaces. The results underscore the importance of comprehensive and efficient solutions in driving successful development projects and fostering positive social and economic changes within marginalized communities.

Table 3 Needs and resources required by the association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar, in order to sustain and enhance operation of their organization following the implementation of Special Areas for Agricultural Development.

Table 3 provides valuable insights into the needs and resources required by association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar, to sustain and enhance the operation of their organization following the implementation of the Special Areas for Agricultural Development. The responses gathered highlight three key areas of importance: unity, training and seminars, and funding support. The unanimous agreement on these crucial needs underscores the significance of cohesive teamwork, continuous learning, and financial backing in ensuring the continued success and growth of the association. These findings align with the principles of effective project evaluation and impact assessment as emphasized by USAID (2023), which stress the importance of attributing observed results to project activities and ruling out alternative explanations to understand the true impact of interventions.

The identification of unity as a fundamental need for the association reflects the importance of teamwork, collaboration, and strong relationships among members to sustain effective operations. This aligns with the existing literature on the essential role of unity and cohesion in driving successful community development initiatives. Additionally, the emphasis on training and seminars as a critical requirement highlights the importance of continuous learning, skill development, and capacity building within the organization. This aligns with the principles of human capital development and ongoing education to enhance organizational effectiveness and adaptability.

Moreover, the recognition of funding support as a significant need underscores the essential role of financial resources in sustaining and enhancing the operation of the association. Securing adequate funding is crucial for implementing projects, maintaining operations, and driving growth and innovation within the organization. These identified needs and resources reflect a comprehensive approach to organizational sustainability, encompassing human capital development, financial stability, and collaborative teamwork to ensure long-term success and resilience.

The findings from Table 3 not only shed light on the specific needs of the association beneficiaries and members but also underscore the interconnectedness between these

needs and the overall sustainability and effectiveness of the organization. By addressing these critical areas of unity, training, and funding support, the association can enhance its capacity to operate efficiently, adapt to challenges, and drive positive outcomes for its members and the community at large. This holistic approach to sustaining and enhancing organizational operations aligns with best practices in project evaluation and impact assessment, emphasizing the importance of understanding and addressing the underlying needs and resources essential for long-term success

Table 4 Impacts of Special Areas on Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects on socio-economic conditions of association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar.

Table 4 provides a comprehensive analysis of the impacts of the Special Areas for Agricultural Development (SAAD) projects on the socio-economic conditions of association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar. The data reveals that a significant proportion of respondents have experienced positive changes in their income levels since the implementation of the SAAD projects. Specifically, 68.06% reported a significant increase, while 31.94% noted a slight increase, indicating a tangible effect on improving economic well-being and potentially enhancing financial stability within the community. These results are consistent with the findings of Hanna et al. (2016), which emphasize the importance of traditional cultural customs and values in the success of development programs and underscore the significant social and environmental repercussions experienced by indigenous communities.

The acknowledgment of a noticeable improvement in financial stability by the majority of respondents (66.67%) highlights the direct impact of the SAAD projects on meeting basic needs and enhancing livelihoods. Additionally, the substantial increase in income-generating opportunities, as affirmed by 83.33% of respondents, underscores the critical role of the SAAD projects in creating avenues for economic empowerment and enhancing financial resources for association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar. These findings align with the literature on the importance of continual engagement and community involvement in mitigation strategies, as recommended by Hanna et al. (2016), to grasp sociocultural factors more thoroughly and ensure sustainable development outcomes.

The positive socio-economic impacts observed in Table 4 are indicative of the effectiveness of the SAAD projects in promoting financial empowerment and livelihood enhancement within the community. The results underscore the alignment between the project's objectives and outcomes, emphasizing its success in addressing economic needs and creating opportunities for growth and development. By connecting the research findings with the related literature, the discussion highlights the consistency between the observed impacts of the SAAD projects and the recommended strategies for engaging with sociocultural factors to achieve positive outcomes. The data from Table 4 not only reinforces the positive socio-economic effects of the SAAD projects but also underscores the importance of cultural sensitivity, community engagement, and empowerment in driving successful development initiatives and fostering sustainable change within marginalized communities.

Table 5 Impact of SAAD Projects on Social and Cultural Transformations among Association Beneficiaries and Members

Table 5 provides compelling evidence of the transformative impact of SAAD projects on the social and cultural fabric of the community in Taft, Eastern Samar. The data reveals a unanimous perception among respondents (100%) that the projects have led to positive changes in social relationships and interactions. This suggests that SAAD projects have fostered a more connected and collaborative community environment, potentially enhancing social cohesion and cooperation among members. This finding aligns with the broader understanding of community development projects as tools for improving socio-economic development, as highlighted by Letsoalo and Moyo (2019). While many projects aim to generate income, assets, and capabilities, their impact on sustaining livelihoods is often unclear, emphasizing the need for comprehensive assessments.

The positive changes in social relationships observed in Table 5 further underscore the importance of community engagement and participation in development initiatives. By fostering a more collaborative environment, SAAD projects have likely contributed to a sense of shared purpose and collective action among community members, potentially leading to greater resilience and sustainability. This aligns with the principles of community development, which emphasize the importance of empowering communities to take ownership of their development processes.

Furthermore, the data reveals a significant influence of SAAD projects on cultural practices related to agriculture. A substantial portion of respondents (65.28%) acknowledged a substantial shift in traditional practices, with the adoption of new agricultural methods introduced through the projects. This demonstrates the tangible impact of SAAD projects on local agricultural customs and techniques, showcasing their ability to drive innovation and adaptation within the community. This finding resonates with the broader understanding of community development projects as agents of change, promoting the adoption of new technologies and practices to enhance livelihoods and sustainability.

The data presented in Table 5 highlights the dual impact of SAAD projects on both social relationships and cultural practices, demonstrating their ability to drive positive transformations and innovations within the community of Taft, Eastern Samar. The findings underscore the importance of considering the social and cultural dimensions of development initiatives, as emphasized by Letsoalo and Moyo (2019). By fostering social cohesion, promoting knowledge-sharing, and facilitating the adoption of new agricultural practices, SAAD projects have likely contributed to the overall well-being and resilience of the community. The data suggests that these projects have not only improved socio-economic conditions but have also played a significant role in shaping the social and

cultural landscape of the community, contributing to a more vibrant and sustainable future.

Table 6 Agricultural Practices and Skills Enhancement

Table 6 provides a compelling account of the positive impact of SAAD projects on agricultural practices and skills enhancement among association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar. The data reveals that all respondents (100%) have experienced improvement in their knowledge and understanding of agricultural practices since the implementation of SAAD projects, highlighting the projects' effectiveness in facilitating learning and skill development within the community. This aligns with the policy outlined in the Republic Act 8435, which emphasizes the importance of prioritizing education and training on science and technology to accelerate social progress and promote human development.

The data further reveals that all respondents (100%) have acquired new skills and techniques related to agriculture as a result of their participation in SAAD projects. These skills encompass a wide range of areas, including crop cultivation, livestock management, soil fertility management, pest and disease control, financial management, organic farming practices, and marketing and value chain management. This comprehensive approach to skills development aligns with the findings of Danso-Abbeam, Ehiakpor, and Aidoo (2018) in Northern Ghana, who noted that extension programs are crucial in agriculturally reliant countries for distributing knowledge about farm technology, supporting adult learning, and enhancing farmers' management and technical abilities.

The data also highlights the significant role of SAAD projects in providing access to training and capacity-building programs focused on agricultural practices, with all respondents (100%) confirming their participation in such programs. This underscores the comprehensive approach of the SAAD projects in equipping beneficiaries and members with the necessary knowledge and skills to enhance their agricultural practices and contribute to the growth of the local agricultural sector. This aligns with the recommendations of Farmer Education (2023) from the USDA National Institute of Food Agriculture, which emphasizes the importance of on-going education for farmers to stay current on rapidly evolving fields of science, technology, and business management, enabling them to integrate the latest advancements into their practices.

The findings from Table 6 demonstrate the effectiveness of SAAD projects in promoting skills enhancement and knowledge acquisition among association beneficiaries and members. The data highlights the projects' alignment with the principles of agricultural modernization and sustainable development, as outlined in the Republic Act 8435 and supported by research findings from Northern Ghana and the USDA National Institute of Food Agriculture. By providing access to training, facilitating knowledge sharing, and equipping farmers with new skills and techniques, SAAD projects are contributing to the

growth of the local agricultural sector, enhancing livelihoods, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices within the community.

Table 7 Potential Long-Term Impact and Sustainability

Table 7 provides a nuanced perspective on the long-term impact and sustainability of the SAAD projects in Taft, Eastern Samar. While the data reveals a strong belief among respondents (100%) that the benefits of the projects will be sustainable in the long run, the unanimous recognition of potential challenges and barriers underscores the need for proactive measures to ensure continued success. This finding aligns with the broader understanding of sustainable development, as articulated by Chladek (2019) and Fallah Shayan et al. (2022), which emphasizes the importance of incorporating long-term sustainability into business strategies and corporate social responsibility initiatives.

The respondents' belief in the sustainability of the SAAD projects suggests a positive outlook on the project's ability to contribute to long-term community development, resonating with Chladek's (2019) argument that sustainable practices can address critical global issues, including climate change, income inequality, and resource depletion. However, the acknowledgment of potential challenges, although unspecified in the data, mirrors the complexities of sustainable development initiatives as discussed by Chladek (2019) and Fallah Shayan et al. (2022). The presence of these challenges underscores the importance of on-going monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation strategies to ensure the long-term impact and sustainability of the projects.

The data presented in Table 7 highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to sustainability, encompassing not only the positive outcomes of the SAAD projects but also the potential obstacles that could hinder their long-term success. This aligns with Fallah Shayan et al.'s (2022) argument that businesses, while essential for generating income and jobs, can also pose risks to the environment and society. By fostering sustainable practices and long-term sustainability, corporate social responsibility (CSR) can mitigate these risks, particularly in today's interconnected world. The data underscores the importance of proactive measures, such as on-going monitoring and evaluation, to mitigate potential risks and ensure the continued positive impact of the SAAD projects on the livelihoods of association beneficiaries and members. This approach aligns with the principles of sustainable development, which emphasize the importance of addressing social, economic, and environmental factors to ensure long-term well-being.

The findings presented in Table 7, while highlighting the potential for long-term sustainability, also serve as a reminder of the complexities and challenges inherent in development initiatives. The data emphasizes the need for a dynamic and responsive approach to ensure the continued success of the SAAD projects, aligning with the call for incorporating long-term sustainability into business strategies and addressing global challenges as advocated by Chladek (2019) and Fallah Shayan et al. (2022). The data underscores the importance of on-going monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation strategies

to address potential challenges and ensure the continued positive impact of the SAAD projects on the livelihoods of association beneficiaries and members.

Conclusions

- 1. Roles and Responsibilities of Officers:** The roles and responsibilities of officers within the association under the SAAD projects in Taft, Eastern Samar play a crucial role in driving socio-economic development and overall transformation within the community. The structured distribution of roles among officers, such as President, Vice President, Treasurer, and Board of Directors, ensures effective decision-making, resource management, and stakeholder engagement. The high level of confidence among officers in the association's ability to operate independently underscores the organization's structural capacity and operational resilience, contributing to its sustainability and success.
- 2. Effectiveness and Sustainability of SAAD Projects:** The SAAD projects in Taft, Eastern Samar have demonstrated a high level of effectiveness and sustainability, as evidenced by the majority of respondents affirming the achievement of project objectives and recommending further implementation. The positive impact of the projects on income levels, financial stability, and income-generating opportunities has been significant, contributing to improved economic well-being and livelihoods within the community. The unanimous recommendation for the SAAD projects reflects their value and relevance in promoting sustainable agricultural development and enhancing community resilience.
- 3. Additional Needs and Resources:** Identified needs and resources, including unity, training and seminars, and funding support, are crucial for sustaining and enhancing the operation of the association following the SAAD projects. Addressing these key areas will contribute to organizational effectiveness, adaptability, and growth, aligning with best practices in promoting community development and ensuring long-term success.
- 4. Impact on Socio-Economic Conditions:** The SAAD projects have had a positive impact on the socio-economic conditions of association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar. The noticeable increase in income levels, financial stability, and income-generating opportunities signifies the effectiveness of the projects in promoting economic empowerment and enhancing livelihoods within the community. These outcomes align with the principles of sustainable development and community resilience, emphasizing the importance of addressing economic needs and creating avenues for growth and development.
- 5. Social and Cultural Transformation:** The SAAD projects have led to positive changes in social relationships and interactions within the community, fostering a more connected and collaborative environment. Additionally, the impact on cultural practices related to agriculture highlights a significant shift towards adopting new agricultural methods, showcasing the projects' role in driving innovation and adaptation within the community. These transformations underscore the projects'

ability to promote social cohesion, knowledge-sharing, and sustainable agricultural practices.

- 6. Agricultural Practices and Skills Enhancement:** The SAAD projects have been highly effective in enhancing knowledge and understanding of agricultural practices among association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar. The acquisition of new skills and techniques related to agriculture, coupled with access to training and capacity-building programs, has empowered individuals to make better-informed decisions, increase income-generating opportunities, and contribute to the growth of the local agricultural sector. These outcomes align with the principles of agricultural modernization and sustainable development, emphasizing the importance of ongoing education and skill development in driving positive change.
- 7. Long-Term Impact and Sustainability:** The SAAD projects have the potential for long-term impact and sustainability, as indicated by the strong belief among respondents in the benefits and improvements brought about by the projects. However, the recognition of potential challenges and barriers underscores the need for proactive measures to ensure continued success. By addressing these challenges, monitoring progress, and adapting strategies, the projects can enhance their long-term sustainability and positive impact on the livelihoods of association beneficiaries and members in Taft, Eastern Samar.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of the SAAD projects in Taft, Eastern Samar:

1. Strengthening Organizational Structure and Governance:

- Formalize and document the roles and responsibilities of association officers. This will ensure clarity, accountability, and a consistent approach to leadership and decision-making.
- Invest in ongoing training and development for association officers. This will equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively lead and manage the organization, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement.
- Promote a strong sense of ownership and responsibility among officers. Encourage a collaborative and supportive environment that values the contributions of all members, fostering a sense of shared purpose and collective action.
- Consider establishing a mentorship program for new officers. This will provide guidance and support, ensuring continuity and knowledge transfer within the organization.

2. Enhancing Project Implementation and Sustainability:

- Continue to prioritize the core elements of the SAAD projects that have proven successful. This includes providing access to training and capacity-building programs, promoting the adoption of new agricultural practices, and fostering economic empowerment through increased income-generating opportunities.
- Proactively address potential challenges and barriers to long-term sustainability. This may involve conducting further research to identify specific challenges, developing mitigation strategies, and implementing ongoing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.
- Ensure that the SAAD projects are adaptable and responsive to the changing needs of the community. This may involve incorporating feedback from beneficiaries and members, adapting project activities to address emerging challenges, and incorporating new technologies and practices as they become available.
- Explore opportunities for collaboration and knowledge sharing with other successful agricultural development projects. This can facilitate the exchange of best practices and enhance the overall effectiveness of the SAAD projects.

3. Fostering Community Engagement and Empowerment:

- Continue to prioritize community engagement and participation in all aspects of the SAAD projects. This includes involving beneficiaries and members in decision-making processes, providing opportunities for feedback and input, and ensuring that the projects are aligned with the needs and priorities of the community.
- Promote a sense of ownership and responsibility among association beneficiaries and members. This can be achieved through participatory approaches, empowering individuals to take an active role in the success of the projects and the overall development of the community.
- Encourage collaboration and knowledge-sharing among community members. This can be facilitated through workshops, training sessions, and peer-to-peer learning opportunities, fostering a culture of innovation and continuous improvement.
- Consider establishing a community advisory board to provide ongoing feedback and guidance on project implementation. This will ensure that the projects remain relevant and responsive to the needs of the community.

4. Securing Long-Term Funding and Resources:

- Develop a sustainable funding strategy for the SAAD projects. This may involve exploring diverse funding sources, including government grants, private sector investment, and community-based fundraising initiatives.
- Ensure that the association has the necessary financial resources to implement project activities, maintain operations, and address emerging needs. This may involve developing a comprehensive budget, managing financial resources effectively, and seeking additional funding support when necessary.

- Promote transparency and accountability in the management of financial resources. This will build trust and confidence among stakeholders and ensure that funds are used effectively to achieve project objectives.
- Explore opportunities for generating income from the SAAD projects themselves. This may involve developing sustainable business models, promoting value-added agricultural products, or establishing partnerships with local businesses.

5. Further Research:

- Conduct further research to identify and address the specific challenges and barriers that could hinder the long-term success of the SAAD projects. This research could involve a larger sample size, a more in-depth qualitative analysis, or a longitudinal study to track the long-term impact of the projects.
- Investigate the potential for replicating the successful aspects of the SAAD projects in other communities within the Philippines or in similar contexts. This would involve a comparative analysis of the project's effectiveness across different regions and communities.

By implementing these recommendations, the SAAD projects in Taft, Eastern Samar can continue to drive positive socio-economic development, promote sustainable agricultural practices, and foster a more resilient and prosperous community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that this research was conducted in compliance with ethical guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Anonymity of respondents was maintained throughout the research process, ensuring that individual identities were not linked to collected data. The well-being of all participants was safeguarded, and no harm or discomfort was caused during the study. The authors declare no conflict of interest in the conduct of this research. All sources of information were properly cited, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. The interpretation of findings was conducted objectively and without bias, ensuring that the results were presented accurately and fairly. The results of this research were used solely for academic purposes and will not be shared with any third parties without the consent of the participants.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to express sincere gratitude to all those who contributed to the successful completion of this research, which was undertaken as a requirement for the Graduate School of Eastern Samar State University, focusing on the field of Agricultural Laws. Special thanks go to Dr. Judith A. Eljera, Subject Instructor and Co-author, for her invaluable guidance, expertise, and unwavering support throughout the study. Her

insights and encouragement were instrumental in shaping the research and ensuring its successful completion. The author is also deeply grateful to the officers and members of the SAAD Projects Association Beneficiaries for their willingness to participate and share their valuable insights. We express our sincere appreciation to the authors of the instruments used in this research for their innovative and insightful work. A heartfelt thank you goes to the author's family for their constant love, support, and understanding during this demanding endeavour. We are eternally thankful to God for providing strength, guidance, and inspiration throughout the journey. Finally, the author extends thanks to friends and relatives for their encouragement and belief in the author's abilities. This research would not have been possible without the generous contributions of all those mentioned above. The author is deeply grateful for their support and collaboration.

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